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SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: A REALITY OR MYTH IN 21ST CENTURY

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Abstract

The present age is the age of development, achievements and success, and for this development the necessary cost has to be pay by everyone. On which cost the development could be done was coined as sustainable development. Sustainable development is a dream which is in dream of every one either an industrialist or bureaucrat or environmentalist or any one irrespective of his or her occupation, living of standard or livelihood. But here the question is whether this dream is achievable or not. Here in the age of development the prime aim of every country is to have development so that they can be in the picture of developed countries rather than developing. But development is at what cost, is on the cost of environment, life, pollution, resources, and the most important the future of the world. In this paper the researcher wants to address the paramount issue whether sustainable development is a myth or a reality which is achievable by the efforts of humankind. Furthermore this paper will discuss the positive and negative issues of sustainable development. Let's see whether we can altogether think about any development with sustainability or not.

Key Words:- Sustainable development, Industrial Development, Environment, Future of world

1. INTRODUCTION

"We have reached a defining moment in human history",

'Sustainable Development" (SD) in 21st century emerged as the latest development catchphrase where a wide range of governmental organizations as well as non-governmental have catch it as the new paradigm of development. These include an incomplete perception of the problems of

poverty and environmental degradation, and confusion about the role of economic growth and about the concepts of sustainability and participation. How these weaknesses can lead to inadequacies and contradictions in policy making is demonstrated in the context of international trade, agriculture, and forestryⁱⁱ.

At least the MDGs had the virtue of being only eight, and also contained clear, quantifiable targets. Take the first MDG: “Halve the proportion of people whose income is less than \$1 a day.” by 2013. Similarly realisable goals or tangible ambitions would be useful for the SDGsⁱⁱⁱ.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

“The critical objectives which follow from the concept of SD” are:

- (1) To review growth;
- (2) To examine the changing quality of growth;
- (3) To meet essential needs for jobs, food, energy, water, and sanitation;
- (4) To ensure a sustainable level of population;
- (5) To preserve and conserving and enhancing the resource base;
- (6) To reorient technology and managing risk;
- (7) To merge environment and economics in decision making; and
- (8) To reorient international economic relations

However, the mainstream formulation of SD suffers from significant weaknesses in:

- (a) Its characterization of the problems of poverty and environmental degradation;
- (b) Its conceptualization of the objectives of development, sustainability and participation;
- (c) The strategy it has adopted in the face of incomplete knowledge and uncertainty.^{iv}

The areas of human activity where there appears to be an absence of policy or no evidence of policy taking place are numerous. Air travel deserves to be singled out here as the most obvious example of this worldwide. There is ample evidence of the negative environmental impacts of

emissions from air transport, but airport expansion is high on the agendas of almost all developed societies and governments are not only failing to regulate air travel, but are rather promoting it. A Scottish example of where policy rhetoric exists but there is a lack of adequate action is in terms of greening the curriculum where very little has been achieved in Higher and Further Education^v.

3. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (SD): AN INTRODUCTION

"What *is* SD?" is being asked increasingly frequently without, however, clear answers forthcoming. SD is in real danger of becoming a cliché like appropriate technology -- a fashionable phrase that everyone pays homage to but nobody cares to define. Four years ago, Tolba lamented that SD had become "an article of faith, a shibboleth; often used, but little explained" (Tolba, 1984a)^{vi}; The United Nations launched the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Meghnad Desai^{vii} believes that these goals are a part and parcel of the UN's "non-stop search for relevance".

In comparison, sustainable development is most of the times interpreted as "sustained change," "sustained growth," or simply "successful" development.

3.1 Sustainable development = development +sustainability

In the mainstream interpretation of SD, ecological sustainability is a desired attribute of any pattern of human activities that is the goal of the developmental process. In other words, SD is understood as "a form of societal change that, in addition to traditional developmental objectives, has the objective or constraint of ecological sustainability." ^{viii}

4. SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: AN ACHIEVABLE DREAM OR A MYTH

The word sustainable becomes so popular that it can be heard everywhere, in all sorts of related, marginally related or even in unrelated contexts. But "sustainable," does not means something which at first conjures up only to sense of environmental virtue, actually belongs agriculture to economics. The examination whether this dream or a myth is based on so many factors, the examination of those factors is here by discussed:-

4.1 To examine what sustainability really means

The Brundtland commission report^{ix} the sustainable development defines as “the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” Or, in the words of countless kindergarten teachers, “Don’t take more than your share^x.” It is important to note here that the present definition is nothing doing with environment it says that ‘decide what is your need and how you can settle it in best ways so that future generation even can take benefit of the same. That point leads to the second myth...

4.2 To analyse whether Sustainability is all about the environment

The sustainability movement itself is not just the word rather its focus was to find different ways for poor nations so that they can catch up to richer ones in better standard of living. The purpose could be achieved only by giving a chance to disadvantaged countries through a better access to natural resources, which includes water, energy and food and all of these can come by one way or another i.e. from the environment only. Paul Hawken^{xi} said “If too many of us use resources inefficiently or generate waste too quickly for the environment to absorb and process, future generations obviously won’t be able to meet their needs”. Here he wants to focus on the appropriate use of resources so that we will gift something to future generations too. If people continue to pour carbon dioxide (CO₂) into the air, for example, we won’t necessarily exhaust resources (there’s plenty of coal still in the ground), but we will change the climate in ways that could very likely impose huge burdens on future generations. The same, of course, goes for the poisonous by-products other than CO₂ from all kinds of human activity, from manufacturing to mining to energy generation to agriculture, that get dumped onto the land and into streams, oceans and the atmosphere^{xii}.

4.3 To examine whether sustainable development is all about recycling

Shana Weber^{xiii} discussed about recycling and observed that “For some reason, recycling was the enduring message that came out of the environmental movement in the early 1970s.” And of course, recycling is important: reusing metals, paper, wood and plastics rather than tossing them reduces the need to extract raw materials from the ground, forests and fossil-fuel deposits. More efficient use of pretty much anything is a step in the direction of sustainability. But it is just a piece of the puzzle. “I deal with the people who run the recycling program here,” Weber notes, “but also with purchasing, dining services, the people who clean the buildings. The most

important areas by far in terms of sustainability are energy and transportation.” If you think you are living sustainably because you recycle, she says, you need to think again^{xiv}.

4.4 To analyse whether Sustainability is too expensive

Another myth about sustainability says it is very expensive, but it is not so, doing an appropriate thing in an appropriate manner by applying the appropriate means. For instance the Pentagon is determined to cut its energy use by a third, both to save money and to reduce its dependence on risky foreign oil supplies.

4.5 To see whether Sustainability means lowering our standard of living

The next myth about sustainability is not at all true. It does mean that ‘to do more effective with less means’, but as Hawken argues that, “Once we start to organize ourselves and innovate within that mind-set, the breakthroughs are extraordinary. They will allow us to achieve greatly superior rates of resource productivity, which in turn allow us to be prosperous, fed, clad, and secure^{xv}.”

4.6 To examine whether new technology is always the answer of sustainability

Another myth is **whether new technology is always the answer of sustainability** or not, it is not necessary that always new technology can sustain the development. In other words, sometimes existing technology can make a huge difference. Sometimes it takes a creative business model. Mark Lee^{xvi} very beautifully observed that “He’s delivering distance, not better batteries, there’s an Italian utility that’s selling its customers hot water, not energy to heat water. It’s a different way of measuring, and it gives the company an incentive to be more efficient so it can be more profitable^{xvii}”.

4.7 To examine whether Sustainability is ultimately a population problem

Although this present hypothesis is not a myth however this represents a false solution. Environmental problem is ultimately a population problem. Population experts agree that the best way to limit population is to educate women and raise the standard of living generally in developing countries. But that strategy cannot possibly happen quickly enough to put a dent in the population on any useful timescale. The U.N. projects that the planet will have to sustain

another 2.6 billion people by 2050. But even at the current population level of 6.5 billion, we're using up resources at an unsustainable rate^{xviii}.

After the analysis of these myths it can be finally observed that sustainability is important and it is the way for healthy development, no one has a right to live on the cost of future. You cannot really declare any practice "sustainable" until you have done a complete life-cycle analysis of its environmental costs. Even then, technology and public policy keep evolving, and that evolution can lead to unforeseen and unintended consequences. The admirable goal of living sustainably requires plenty of thought on an ongoing basis^{xix}.

5. CONCLUSION: DILEMMAS AND AGENDAS

"If you want to go from applause to action, you have to add another step: accountability, Targets without accountability are not worth having^{xx}"

The 193 member countries of the United Nations have unanimously adopted a landmark set of development goals that are intended to galvanise and guide the world's efforts to eradicate poverty, end hunger and address climate change by 2030. The 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) are broken down into 169 specific targets that each country has committed to try and achieve voluntarily over the next 15 years. For richer donor countries – such as the UAE – the 2030 agenda also provides a framework for greater coordination of efforts to finance the achievement of the targets in developing countries^{xxi}.

"We have to tackle the reasons why people flee and are driven from their homes," she said. "Our 2030 agenda provides exactly the right framework^{xxii}"

The proponents of Sustainable development are faced with a predicament that affects any political action and social change. In other words, Sustainable development is an attempt to have one's cake and eat it too.

More specifically, proponents and analysts of SD need to:

(a) To clearly reject the attempts (and temptation) to focus on economic growth as a means to poverty removal and/or environmental sustainability;

(b) To recognize the internal inconsistencies and inadequacies in the theory and practice of neoclassical economics, particularly as it restates to environmental and distributional issues: in economic analyses, move away from arcane mathematical models toward exploring empirical questions such as limits to the substitution of capital for resources, impacts of different sustainability policies on different economic systems, etc.

(c) To accept the existence of structural, technological and cultural causes of both poverty and environmental degradation: develop methodologies for estimating the relative importance of and interactions between these causes in specific situations: and explore political, institutional and educational solutions to them:

(d) To understand the multiple dimensions of sustainability, and attempt to develop measures, criteria and principles for them; and

(e) To explore what patterns and levels of resource demand and use would be compatible with different forms or levels of ecological and social sustainability, and with different notions of equity and social justice.^{xxiii}.

• Sustainable development policy should reflect local values and be capable of delivery through existing national and local decision-making frameworks. To achieve this better understanding is needed of the scale, level, magnitude and spatial dimensions of both the problem of unsustainable activities in Scotland and their solutions. • The biggest gains for sustainability are most likely to result from legislative and institutional changes rather than from individual or household behaviour change. The Executive should consider separate areas of policy delivery (such as waste, transport, and energy) and decide whether institutional, legislative or public behaviour change is the most appropriate and effective route for advancing a given sustainability goal. • Where public behaviour change is considered the most fruitful way forward, a step by-step approach is needed, in which external barriers are removed before psychological or attitudinal factors are addressed. It is much easier to change behaviour through automatic responses to changes in opportunity than to challenge ingrained attitudes and perceptions. Provision of practical information is a key element in behaviour change, but campaigns need to be well targeted and coordinated with other measures. • There should be better integration

between social and green procurement to create a more holistic sustainable procurement approach. There is a pressing need to introduce mechanisms whereby assessment and evaluation of sustainable procurement can be undertaken and to harmonize sustainable public procurement with trade policies. • Awareness-raising to enable consumers to understand the implications of their food purchasing decisions and the way goods and services are used after purchase should be key priorities. • Making evident the links between obesity, nutrition and the sustainability of people's daily lifestyle is likely to be one of the most effective ways of promoting more sustainable levels of consumption and encouraging people to consume and waste less. In tandem with such information campaigns, people need to be offered the opportunity to buy more eco-friendly products and to adopt less environmentally damaging lifestyles. • There is a need for a systematic approach to strategic infrastructure provision through a national spatial perspective to replace competitive bidding for infrastructure resources. Community planning needs to more directly recognise sustainable development and proactively aim to promote this through all planning decisions. Strategic Environmental Assessment in relation to plans and programmes, and Environmental Impact Assessment, in relation to particular development applications, may be suitable mechanisms for this. • A need and considerable opportunities exist for better integration of sustainable development throughout the education curriculum in Scotland^{xxiv}.

Secretary-general Ban Ki-moon (13 June 1944) is a South Korean statesman and politician who is the eighth Secretary-General of the United Nations. Before becoming Secretary-General, Ban was a career diplomat in South Korea's Ministry of Foreign Affairs and in the United Nations.

ⁱⁱ Sharachchandra M., "Sustainable Development: A Critical Review", *World Development*, Vol.19, No. 6, 1991, pp. 607-621.

ⁱⁱⁱ Sholto Byrnes, "Sustainable development: achievable or just a dream?", June 2, 2015 Updated: June 2, 2015 06:31 PM, available at: <http://www.thenational.ae/opinion/comment/sustainable-development-achievable-or-just-a-dream>.

^{iv} *Supra* note ii.

^v University of Westminster and the Law School & University of Strathclyde, "Sustainable development: A review of international literature", The Centre for Sustainable Development & Scottish Executive Social Research, 2006, available at: www.scotland.gov.uk/socialresearch.

^{vi} Mostafa Kamal Tolba (8 December 1922) is an Egyptian scientist who served 17-year tenure as Executive Director of the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). Tolba graduated from Cairo University in 1943, and obtained a PhD from Imperial College London five years later. He established his own school in microbiology at Cairo University's Faculty of Science, and also taught at the University of Baghdad during the 1950s. In addition to his academic career, Tolba worked in the Egyptian civil service. Tolba led Egypt's delegation to the landmark 1972 Stockholm Conference, which established the United Nations Environment Programme. Tolba became UNEP's Deputy Executive Director immediately after the conference, and two years later was promoted to Executive Director. During his long tenure (1975–1992), he played a role in the fight against ozone depletion, which culminated with the Vienna Convention (1985) and the Montreal Protocol (1987).

^{vii} Meghnad Jagdishchandra Desai, Baron Desai (10 July 1940) is an Indian-born, naturalised British economist and Labour politician. He unsuccessfully stood for the Speaker in the British House of Lords in 2011, the first ever

non-UK born candidate to do so. He has been awarded the Padma Bhushan, the third highest civilian award in the Republic of India, in 2008.

^{viii} *Supra* note ii.

^{ix} The World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), the Brundtland Commission's mission is to unite countries to pursue sustainable development together. The Chairman of the Commission, Gro Harlem Brundtland, was appointed as a former Secretary General of the United Nations, in December 1983. At the time, the UN General Assembly realized that there was a heavy deterioration of the human environment and natural resources. To rally countries to work and pursue sustainable development together, the UN decided to establish the Brundtland Commission. Gro Harlem Brundtland was the former Prime Minister of Norway and was chosen due to her strong background in the sciences and public health. The Brundtland Commission officially dissolved in December 1987 after releasing *Our Common Future*, also known as the *Brundtland Report*, in October 1987, a document which coined, and defined the meaning of the term "Sustainable Development". *Our Common Future* won the University of Louisville Grawemeyer Award in 1991. The organization Centre for Our Common Future was started in April 1988 to take the place of the Commission.

^x Lemonick D. Michael, "Scientific American Top 10 Myths about Sustainability, Even advocates for more responsible, environmentally benign ways of life harbor misunderstandings of what "sustainability" is all about", Mar 1, 2009, available at: <http://www.scientificamerican.com/article/top-10-myths-about-sustainability/?page=1>

^{xi} Paul Hawken, was the author (his latest book is *Blessed Unrest: How the Largest Movement in the World Came into Being, and Why No One Saw it Coming*) and entrepreneur (he's a co-founder of the Smith & Hawken garden tools company) who helped to found the sustainability movement: "We have an economy where we steal the future, sell it in the present, and call it GDP [gross domestic product]."

^{xii} *Supra* note x

^{xiii} Shana Weber directs the Office of Sustainability and has served as lecturer in the Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology at Princeton University. Dr. Weber has coordinated university efforts in comprehensive campus-based sustainability study and operational implementation since 2006. Her past research areas include the intersection of climate change impacts and land use history, and population biology of culturally-significant wetland vegetation. Current research interest includes climate-change driven population dynamics of high altitude small mammals, and collaborative applied sustainability research across academic institutions.

^{xiv} *Supra* note x

^{xv} *Id* at p. 2.

^{xvi} Mark Lee, CEO of the London consulting firm Sustainability

^{xvii} *Supra* note x, at p. 3

^{xviii} *Id* at p.4

^{xix} *Ibid*.

^{xx} David Miliband, was the CEO of the International Rescue Committee, in remarks at a Unicef event. David (15 July 1965) is a British Labour Party politician who was the Secretary of State for Foreign and Commonwealth Affairs from 2007 to 2010 and the Member of Parliament (MP) for South Shields from 2001 to 2013. Aged 29 he became Tony Blair's Head of Policy whilst the Labour Party was in opposition, and he was a major contributor to Labour's manifesto for the 1997 election, which brought the party to power in a landslide victory. Blair subsequently made him head of the Prime Minister's Policy Unit from 1997 to 2001, at which point Miliband was elected to Parliament for the seat of South Shields.

^{xxi} Taimur Khan, "What are the United Nations' sustainable development goals?", September 27, 2015 Updated: September 28, 2015 12:11 AM, available at: <http://www.thenational.ae/world/americas/20150927/what-are-the-united-nations-sustainable-development-goals>

^{xxii} Angela Dorothea Merkel (17 July 1954) is a German politician and former research scientist who has been the Chancellor of Germany since 2005 and the Leader of the Christian Democratic Union (CDU) since 2000. She is the first woman to hold either office.

^{xxiii} *Supra* note ii

^{xxiv} *Supra* note v

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